

washed of S.S. 4.5' X1/B.O.D. maintained at 180°. Injection port and detector block were maintained at 270° with a flow rate of 40 ml/min with a chart speed of 15 mm/min.

The percentage composition of the acids were calculated based on peak areas⁵ and it was found to be composed of palmitic (18.10%), oleic (17.60%), linoleic (60.60%), linolenic (2.20%) and small amount of stearic acids.

Chromatographic resolution of the unsaponifiable matter resulted in the isolation of β -amyrin, m.p. 197-98° and β -sitosterol, m.p. 136-37° which were identified by direct comparison with authentic samples.

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Chemical Constituents of *Cephalotaxus griffithii*

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CEPHALOTAXUS griffithii HK (Fam. Cephalotaxaceae), collected from Nainital, has been investigated for its chemical constituents and led to the isolation of amentoflavone, sequoiaflavone, apigenin, ginkgetin, mono-O-methyl-C-methyl amentoflavone and quercitrin. 1,6-C-Methyl-1,7-O-methyl amentoflavone constitutes the second report of isolation and characterization of naturally occurring C-methyl biflavones.

Finely ground dried leaves of *Cephalotaxus griffithii* (3 kg) were successively extracted with petrol (40-60°), benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate and finally with acetone. The last two extracts were concentrated and chromatographed over silicagel to furnish six bands labelled as CGI, CGII,

CGIII, CGIV, CGV and CGVI, in order of increasing R_f values. All these bands were separated by preparative tlc (BPF, 36:9:5)² and eluted by acetone mixed with pyridine (2%). CGI (0.2 g) obtained, gave a single spot on tlc, R_f 0.18, m.p. 320°. The yellow solid mass (80 mg) was methylated to give hexa-O-methyl amentoflavone (50 mg), m.p. 173-74°, R_f 0.40. Acetylation (Ac_2O /pyridine) of yellow solid (80 mg) yielded a white solid which crystallized from $CHCl_3$ -MeOH to give amentoflavone hexaacetate, m.p. 242-43°.

The identity of sequoiaflavone and apigenin was established by direct comparison of their acetate and methylethers with those of authentic samples. (m.p., m.m.p., fluorescence in uv light and nmr data).

CGIV, m.p. 350° (decomp), $C_{30}H_{16}O_8(OMe)_2$, λ_{max} (ethanol): 271 nm band I, 335 nm band II. Tetraacetyl derivative, $C_{30}H_{12}O_4(OMe)_4(OAc)_4$, was prepared, m.p., 265-267°. λ_{max} (ethanol): 211, 248-258, 317 nm, finally confirmed as dimethyl ether of amentoflavone (ginkgetin) by comparison with an authentic sample.

CGV, m.p. above 338°, R_f 0.39, $C_{32}H_{22}O_{10}$, M^+566 . Mass spectrum of its methylether showed mol. ion peak at M^+636 and base peak at m/e 621, m.p. 234, R_f 0.45. The compound was finally established as 1,6-C-methyl-1,7-O-methyl amentoflavone by comparison (co.tlc, uv, nmr and mass) with authentic sample³.

CGVI, $C_{31}H_{20}O_{11}$, λ_{max} 275, 352 m μ was hydrolysed (10% HCl) and aglycone and sugar were chromatographed with authentic samples. The sugar was found to be rhamnose. The aglycone, m.p. 182-185° was identical in all respects with quercetin. The structure of CGVI was finally confirmed as quercetin 3-rhamnoside by comparison of its nmr spectral data with that of authentic sample.

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